

School mathematics boost for first semester students having major problems with maths

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Abstract

Successful technical studies rely on a solid mathematical base. Our undergraduate candidates must have solid maths knowledge at least at the intermediate school level to follow their very first university lectures. However, the admission requirements for technical higher education are much lower than actually needed. For this reason, many candidates start their technical studies with insufficient mathematical skills. Long breaks between school and study can also cause mathematical knowledge decay. In order to close the gap between actual and necessary mathematical level, we are offering a short refresher school maths course before the first semester starts and a long boost course during the first semester. In this report we evaluated four post-pandemic semesters and looked at the possible impact of these two interventions on the first semester maths exam. Our findings show, that students who participated in the short refresher course took and passed the first maths exam significantly more often than students who did not take the course. We conclude, the first group is highly motivated to study. Moreover, students of electrical engineering, who just failed their placement test at the beginning of the first semester (reached 40-50% points) and had to take part in the one semester long booster course passed their first maths exam as well as those students, who just passed the placement test, i.e. reached 50-60% points: no significant differences could be found between those groups. This may indicate the positive impact of the long booster course.

Keywords: school mathematics deficits, refreshing course, placement test.

Introduction

Undergraduate candidates often lack the necessary maths skills for engineering study. Intermediate level mathematics, such as adding fractions, operating on symbols, calculating terms, using binomial formulas and power rules, plotting simple function graphs, calculating logarithms and trigonometric functions, solving equations and equations systems, and handling units, are very often unknown to our students. All of these themes are covered in our two remedial courses and placement tests.

Our students also need to understand that maths is not something they can just pay little attention to and forget about, as they did it at school. We try to show them that maths is not a goal in itself, but a necessary step for future studies. For this reason, we include many mathematical problems related to daily life or technology itself in the refresher courses. This makes maths more interesting.

Methods

The first short refresher (SR) course is open to all students at the university and lasts one week, just before semester starts. It is also a great opportunity to get to know each other and the campus. The latter is undoubtedly the main reason why that course is well attended.

At the very begin of the first semester a placement test (PT) in maths takes place for students of electrical engineering. The test starts with simple questions, e.g. adding numerical fractions, goes through square roots, logarithms, 2x2 linear equation systems, Pythagoras' theorem with analysis of units, quadratic equations with parameters, factorization of symbolic fractions with the use of binomial formulas and analysis of quadratic function.

The second, long refresher (LR) course is mandatory for students who failed their placement test at the begin of the semester, i.e. reached less than 50%. Students, who obtained 50-75% of the points and therefore passed the test, are invited to join up the booster course. That course takes place during the first semester, twice a week for 90 minutes, i.e. a total of 15 x 90 minutes. We monitor the progress of maths skills through written homework four times in the semester and two unsupervised online tests. Only students, who have passed every homework assignment, i.e. gained more than 50%, are permitted to take the maths exam in the first semester (MA1 exam). We decided to try unsupervised homework as a way to measure progress because we know that supervised tests always lead to stress. We deliberately sought to avoid the latter, since every student must pass three supervised tests during the regular first semester maths lecture (regardless of the refresher course) to be allowed to take the first maths exam.

Both refresher courses are carried out in a similar way: first a topic, e.g. adding fractions, is presented and solution methods for one or two tasks are demonstrated. Afterwards students are given another task on the topic, which they have to solve independently or in small groups. After a set time, the proposed solutions are discussed. This point is tricky. It is about how to show the students that their solutions are often wrong and where they went wrong in their reasoning without upsetting them or making them feel stupid. The latter may lead to student absence in the following meetings, since the attendance is not compulsory.

The first remedial course is supervised by students, whereas the second course is run by university staff. Student-tutors may significantly lower the inhibition threshold for asking questions, an important skill in gaining understanding. In the second course, we must first gain the students' confidence. We want them to be able to ask questions or share their own solutions.

Findings

We analyse the possible influence of the remedial courses for four semesters, starting with winter semester 2022, up to summer semester 2024, since we admit new students every half a year. Our university began offering the short refresher course in summer

2023, so it has been available for evaluation for three semesters so far. The long refresher course is being offered to students in our department for a much longer time, but most of the results are only available since winter 2022.

We analysed the impact of the short refresher (SR) course on the maths (MA1) exams after the first semester. Students who participated in the SR course wrote the MA1 exam more often (21 out of 27), and passed it more often (20 out of 21) than students who did not participate (45 out of 71 and 35 out of 45 respectively), as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Violinplot of MA1 exam results for four semesters. The results are split between participants of the SR course (orange) and students who did not participate in the SR course (blue). On the left-hand scale, “1” is the best grade, “4” is “sufficient”, and anything above “4” means that the MA1 exam has been failed.

The placement test (PT) concerned intermediate school mathematics. Questions about factorization, fractional and root equations, quadratic equations with a parameter, power rules and logarithms were found the most difficult, with the least points achieved. The easy questions included adding numerical fractions, simple Pythagoras’ theorem, analysis of simple quadratic equations and a simple 2x2 linear equation systems.

Of the 63 students who passed the placement test, 51 also passed the maths exam, two failed and eight left the faculty. Out of 87 students, who failed the placement test, 67 successfully completed the long refresher course and 40 of them passed the MA1-exam. A short overview is given in Figure 2.

PT	63		87		
LR course			67	20	
MA1	2	51	40	14	13
passed			failed	not admitted to MA1-exam/ no interest/left the department/...	

Figure 2. Consolidated results of the placement test (PT), long refreshing (LR) course and MA1 exam for four semesters: winter 2022 - summer 2024.

The relationship between the PT results and the MA1 exam grades can be found in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Correlations between placement test results and MA1 exam grades. MA1 exam grade “1” means the best grade, “4” is “sufficient”, and anything above “4” means that the MA1 exam has been failed.

The Pearson's correlation coefficient between PT results and MA1 exam grades was -0.59 and there was a significant difference in MA1 exam grades between the group of students who participated in the LR course and those who did not. However, based on the PT results alone, one could not predict the MA1 exam results.

We analysed the group of the LR course participants, who passed the MA1 exam. Figure 4 shows the distribution of PT percentage points achieved by the LR course participants and how many of them passed the MA1 exam. The high PT scores did not guarantee MA1 success, nor did lower PT scores exclude it.

Figure 4: Histogram of the placement test results for the LR course participants only. The numbers above each bin show how many students from that bin passed the MA1 exam later on.

When comparing the MA1 exam results for the strongest group in LR course, who just failed the placement test (obtained 40-50% points) including the LR course volunteers, with the group of students who just passed the test (obtained 50-60% points) and therefore did not take part in the LR course, no differences could be found. It is worth mentioning that the first group achieved significantly lower PT scores in its most difficult questions: factorizations and powers and logarithms, as can be seen in Table 1. The differences could be levelled out within one semester.

	p-2samp- KS	40<PT<50 + volunteers	50<PT<60
PT (in total)	3.12e-14	45.5	55.8
PT: factorisation (max. 12 points)	0.0108	2.67	4.17
PT: powers and logarithms (max. 13 points)	0.000363	4.11	6.66
MA1 exam (German score)	0.59	2.97	2.95

Table1. Results of two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov for the group which just passed the PT (50<PT<60) against the group which just failed it (40<PT<50). P-values of that test and the mean values for both groups.

Conclusions and Outlook

We conclude that students participating in the short refresher (SR) course were really interested in successful study, since they could take and pass the first maths (MA1) exam significantly more often than students who did not take this course.

The placement test for students of electrical engineering at the beginning of the semester correlated coarsely with the MA1 exam at the end of the semester, and thus gave a rough insight about math skills. However, it could not be used to predict future maths success. Moreover, students who just failed the placement test (PT) at the beginning of the semester showed the most interest in and benefited the most from the long refresher (LR) course. This was clearly reflected in their MA1 exam grades, which were as good as those of students who just passed the PT.

We are confident that our steps taken to bridge the gap between the existing and required mathematical knowledge and skills of the first semester students have been successful. However, our future approach will change slightly due to the common use of the generative artificial intelligence (GenAI). Over the past two semesters, GenAI has partially dominated the way homework is solved. On the one hand, we encourage students to use GenAI as another cognitive tool or personal tutor, while retaining their own critical reasoning skills. On the other hand, there is a growing danger of mindlessly rewriting everything the AI has written. Unfortunately, the thoughtless use of GenAI last semester leads us to change the format to supervised tests during the booster course.